

Strathmore
UNIVERSITY

Deliverable

Prototype Interfaces with Analytical Workflows

Task 4f

31/3/2025

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1.1 Background

The platform team identified that CKAN provides an API option to retrieve CSV data from the data repository. We decided to test this functionality to assess whether it would be a suitable option for users of the repository. Some team members also highlighted its potential benefits. The platform team set up and developed the API to integrate it into the Kenya data repository and proceeded with testing.

1.2 Meeting 1 – 27.02.2025

The platform team, together with the team at Imperial, held an initial meeting to test the API. The tutorial covered the following steps:

- Accessing the data repository
- Navigating the user interface
- Finding a CSV dataset using the search bar
- Using the API button to retrieve the code (Figure 1)
- Using the code to retrieve the dataset

Figure 1. Retrieving the code

Initially, there was some confusion about how to use the code. We realized that the process is not entirely straightforward, as it requires downloading the appropriate CKAN packages depending on <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15112741> - v1.0

the programming language being used and then generating a token. During the meeting, we successfully created a token; however, we encountered some issues, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Issues

One suggested option was to refer to the documentation, but this seemed too time-consuming. As a result, another meeting was scheduled to explore ways to simplify the process.

1.3 Meeting 2 – 20.03.2025

After the issues encountered in the initial test, we worked on a solution and tested it again with the Imperial team. The solution involved sharing a code example to simplify the process as presented in the box 1.

Box 1. Code example

```
from ckanapi import RemoteCKAN

API_TOKEN = "" # insert your API token here as a string

rc = RemoteCKAN('http://kenya.swedencentral.cloudapp.azure.com/', apikey=API_TOKEN)

result = rc.action.datastore_search(
    resource_id="76ce97b0-528e-4d70-9fa8-11ea0d012cf5",
```

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15112741> - v1.0

```

    limit=5,

    q="Nairobi",

)

print(result['records'])

```

This code allowed us to retrieve the data successfully. We confirmed that providing a code example makes using the API easier and less time-consuming.

```

Windows PowerShell
conda-forge/noarch::urllib3-2.3.0-pyhd8ed1ab_0
conda-forge/noarch::win_inet_pton-1.1.0-pyh7428d3b_8
conda-forge/win-64::zstandard

Proceed ([y]/n)? y

Downloading and Extracting Packages:

Preparing transaction: done
Verifying transaction: done
Executing transaction: done
(wesm) PS C:\Users\rheredia\OneDrive - Imperial College London\Desktop\api> python
Python 3.13.2 | packaged by Anaconda, Inc. | (main, Feb 6 2025, 18:49:14) [MSC v.1929 64 bit (AMD64)] on win32
Type "help", "copyright", "credits" or "license()" for more information.
>>> from ckanapi import RemoteCKAN
>>> API_TOKEN = "pablito"
>>> rc = RemoteCKAN('http://kenya.swedencentral.cloudapp.azure.com/', apikey=API_TOKEN)
>>>
>>> result = rc.action.datastore_search(
...     resource_id="76ce97b0-528e-4d70-9fa8-11ea0d012cf5",
...     limit=5,
...     q="Nairobi",
... )
>>> print(result['records'])
[{'_id': 47, 'COUNTY Name': 'Nairobi City', 'COUNTY Id': 'NI', 'County Number': 'C48', '2019': 4397073, '2020': 4515607, '2021': 4593
757, '2022': 4671906, '2023': 4750056, '2024': 4828205, '2025': 4906355, '2026': 4978028, '2027': 5049701, '2028': 5121374, '2029': 5
193047, '2030': 5264721, '2031': 5330961, '2032': 5397201, '2033': 5463441, '2034': 5529681, '2035': 5595922, '2036': 5657198, '2037'
: 5718474, '2038': 5779750, '2039': 5841026, '2040': 5902303, '2041': 5957848, '2042': 6013393, '2043': 6068938, '2044': 6124483, '20
45': 6180029, '2046': 6235574, '2047': 6291119, '2048': 6346664, '2049': 6402209, '2050': 6457754, '2051': 6513299, '2052': 6568844,
'2053': 6624389, '2054': 6679934, '2055': 6735479, '2056': 6791024, '2057': 6846569, '2058': 6902114, '2059': 6957659, '2060': 701320
4, '2061': 7068749, '2062': 7124294, '2063': 7179839, '2064': 7235384, '2065': 7290929, '2066': 7346474, '2067': 7402019, '2068': 745
7564, '2069': 7513109, '2070': 7568654, 'rank': 0.057308756}]
>>>

```

1.4 Conclusion

The API is a useful tool, and we were able to use it successfully. However, resolving issues required two meetings. The examples provided by CKAN can be difficult to navigate, and going through the documentation is time-consuming. Providing a clear example using a dataset from the repository significantly improves usability. It is also important to remember that an API token must be created and the necessary CKAN packages must be downloaded for successful implementation.